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NANOTECHNOLOGY IN MANAGEMENT OF PSORIASIS: A FOCUS ON HERBAL THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a hyper proliferative, autoimmune skin disorder. Despite the fact that many therapies are there in treating psoriasis, no single treatment gives complete and satisfactory cure. There are several therapeutic agents used topically and systemically but they have adverse effects. As an alternative for these drugs, herbal medicine have been widely used. These have better therapeutic value and have less side effects. Nano herbal drug delivery systems have a great future for increasing the activity and succeeding in dealing with the problems related with medicinal plants. Various marketed herbal formulations are available.

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INTRODUCTION: [1]

Psoriasis is a skin disease which is distinguished by massive proliferation, thick inflammatory cell infiltrates, generation of new blood vessels, modifications in lymphatic structure and impaired differentiation of epidermis. It is an autoimmune disorder where environment and genetic components have a major function.

Historical perspective and epidemiological studies: [1, 2]

Psoriasis is an inflammatory disease which has been existing from ancient times and is cosmopolitan. It was initially described in the Corpus Hippocraticum. The term psora was used by Hippocrates (460-377 BC), that means, 'to itch'. In simple terms Psoriasis is a non communicable regular skin disorder that leads to instant skin cell reproduction leading in red, dry patches of thickened skin. The dry flakes and skin scales are the result of the instant and sudden formation of skin cells. Psoriasis commonly affects the skin of the elbows, knees, and scalp. Skin sores can not only be itchy and defaced, in 10-30% of patients there can also be nail dystrophy associated with psoriatic arthritis. The swelling in the joints is alike in few forms to Rheumatic arthritis (RA), although in psoriasis it is a seronegative arthritis (no rheumatoid factor is present in the blood). Thus the various clinical evidences of psoriasis make it more than a skin disorder, as it hampers certain usual daily actions, like using hands, sleeping, walking etc. The Crohn disease which is an inflammatory bowel disorder, is one of the most serious problem related with psoriasis other than arthritis.

Both the sex are equally affected by this disorder and is seen at all ages, especially first time between the ages 15-25 years. It is a lifelong inflammatory disease.

Pathophysiology of Psoriasis:

Very rapid multiplication of keratinocytes occur in people having psoriasis and their movement from the stratum basale (basal layer) to the upper layer of epidermis occurs in 4 days. Thick dry patches or plaques form, as the skin does not shed the cells quickly[3]. In some people very mild psoriasis exists which cannot be even suspected as a skin disorder. Others have very severe psoriasis where almost whole body is covered with scaly, thick and red skin. Despite the fact that psoriasis occurs in population of all age groups, i.e., paediatrics to geriatrics, generally it is diagnosed in adolescence of a person.

The other causative factors for psoriasis are genetics, sudden changes in genes (mutations), climate, mental or emotional strain, contagion, and wounds [4, 5].

The major pathological phenomenon associated with psoriasis are [6]

1. T cell activation
2. Activated T cells migration into the skin
3. Reactivation of T cells in dermis and epidermis

Types of psoriasis:**Plaque psoriasis: [6, 7]**

It is also known as psoriasis vulgaris, which generally occurs (almost 80-85%). It is usually seen on elbows, knees, scalp and lower back. Symptoms include,

- Spherical lesions which ranges about 0.99 cm to several cms in width, and may further grow into patches.
- Red colored lesions which are encrusted with silvery, loose and shining skin.
- Lesions that are generally seen on the elbows, knees, and trunk.

Causes due to which this type occurs are generally infections, skin abrasion, medications, sunlight, strain, smoking and drinking.

Fig 1: Plaque psoriasis [8]

Guttate psoriasis: [6]

It is also known as rain drop psoriasis and is the second general form (around 10%) seen in population with psoriasis. Symptoms are

- Several minute rain drops sized lesions
- Lesions grow instantly, generally on the trunk, arms, legs, and scalp
- Eruption of lesions which may occur along with any upper respiratory infection.

Causes are streptococcal infection, viral or bacterial contagions, skin wounds and burns, insect bites etc, sunlight, medicine etc.

Fig 2: Guttate psoriasis [8].

Psoriatic arthritis: [6, 9]

It is a condition in which swelling occurs which shows impact on the joints. Generally appears in 6% to 40% of population having this skin disorder.

Symptoms of psoriatic arthritis include:

- Inflated, sore, thick, and painful joints,
- Above signs may be seen earlier, along with, or following the development of symptoms of the skin.
- In the hands and feet, joint symptoms are seen.

Causes are shock or wounds on skin, medications, agents that cause irritation of skin, smoking and drinking etc

Fig 3: Psoriatic arthritis [8].

Pustular psoriasis: [6]

It can occur as patches which are small or wide spread on areas of feet, hands or fingertips. Seen in 5% or less population having psoriasis. Symptoms are,

- Fluid-filled lesions which are seen on soles and palms. Very scaly skin.
- Alterations in nail.
- Eruptions which are seen after discontinuation of certain medications and creams.

Causes are pregnancy, overexposure to UV light, systemic steroids, contagions, mental and emotional strain, and sudden withdrawal of certain medications.

Fig 4: Pustular psoriasis [8].

Erythroderma, or exfoliative psoriasis: [6]

It is a very uncommon type that may be damaging or lethal. In population with this type, along with skin, symptoms are seen on whole body like

- Inflation and soreness which occurs on entire body skin. The skin may slough off and is generally itchy and tender.
- Incapable to monitor temperature of the body and chills.

Causes are use of steroid, extreme sun burn, strain, drinking alcohol, contagions, sensitivity etc.

Fig 5: Erythroderma [8].

Nail psoriasis: [6]

Along with building up of skin cells under epidermis, in half of the psoriasis population they even develop under nails, which becomes impenetrable. They mostly split and in extreme cases, they fall down or collapse. Yellow or brownish red spots are seen below the nail.

Causes of this type is not known exactly, but generally it is considered having a genetic factor. [10]

Fig 6: Nail psoriasis [8].

Genetic factors

Human genome scans show almost nine various loci which are susceptible to psoriasis (PSORS1-9). PSORS-1, is the main genetic factor of this disorder, which results up to 50% of genetic sensitivity to psoriasis. The risk of psoriasis may be increased due to certain variations and changes, which are related with four auto immune diseases: type 1 diabetes, Celiac disease, Grave's disease and rheumatoid arthritis describing that all above disorders have the same genetic factors. [11]

Trigger Factors

Climate, strain, wounds, medicines are indirect causes and infections like HIV, one of the uncommon forms of Human Papilloma viruses (HPV) like EV-HPV, Streptococcal infections in upper respiratory tract like sinusitis, tonsillitis are mostly important in triggering the disease process that commences and intensifies psoriasis. [12]

Diagnosis:

Based on clinical studies such as skin rash, alterations in nails, joint involvement etc psoriasis is diagnosed. Occasionally patients show uncommon skin sores that have to be distinguished from mycosis fungicides, seborrheic dermatitis, tinea, discoid lupus or undesignated skin symptoms like very little scaling of the scalp, isolated flexural erythema, or genital lesions. Thorough inspection of the body sites must be done to reveal unrecognised, clinically useful characteristics, and occasionally a skin biopsy may be required. Fusions of the various types may develop occasionally along with or later in the same patient. The silvery white scales, which are filled with dark pink or red lesions having prominent edges can be separated easily for diagnosis of psoriasis. After scraping off the moist skin, tiny blood droplets appear under the scales which are seen under pinkish moist tender skin. Scraping or skin biopsy and blood analysis may be necessary sometimes, to approve the diagnosis. [4]

Severity of disease: [13]

The extremity of this disease occurs from one or two small flaky swollen patches to extensive pustular psoriasis which in atypical cases can be lethal. To help in determining the suitable treatment for a patient, physicians generally classify psoriasis as mild to severe which is usually done based on percentage of skin impacted.

- Mild: Affected body area is < 3% affected. Less than 2% of the skin is affected in most cases of psoriasis.
- Moderate: 3-10% skin is impacted.
- Severe: >10% of the body is influenced.

Treating severe psoriasis is harder. However, though not categorized under severe psoriasis, few types of psoriasis are unaffected to treatment which include,

- Hand and Foot psoriasis (Any psoriasis that occur on palms and soles)
- Psoriasis that is seen in the fold of the skin (Inverse)
- Psoriatic arthritis
- Scalp psoriasis

Therapies to treat psoriasis:

There are various therapies for treating psoriasis. Any therapy should be considered on long term basis. General therapies present for treating psoriasis are systemic agents (medicines within the body), topical agents (medicines applied to the skin) and phototherapy. All these treatments may be used single or in combination with one another. Best treatment for the individual is determined by the physician situated on the kind and extremity of psoriasis.

Various approaches are:

Topical Therapy:

These are the medications that are directly applied on the skin and are the first line of therapy options. Topical creams, sprays and lotions are very effective for mild psoriasis and is also safe to use. Corticosteroids, vitamin D-3 derivatives [14], retinoids, coal tar or anthralin [15] are the main topical treatments. Combination of these preparations can be given sometimes. For example, keratolytics are often added to topical preparations.

Because of interference with each other some preparations should never be mixed together. For example, when salicylic acid is added to calcipotriene cream or ointment (a form of vitamin D-3) it inactivates the substance, while salicylic acid is required to be to medicines like anthralin to work effectively.

Photo therapy: [13]

Skin would be exposed to ultraviolet (UV) radiation in case of failure of topical treatments in achieving desired goal. This type of treatment is called phototherapy. This therapy includes subjection to UV radiations with the help of special apparatus utilizing fluorescent light source discharging specific wavelength of radiation. Psoriasis responds to ultraviolet rays. Symptoms get reduced on frequent subjection to sun or artificial ultraviolet rays. Methods are:

- Subjection to ultraviolet B light, i.e., UVB(290-320nm)
- Subjection to UV rays (320-400nm) combined with the drug psoralen, i.e., PUVA, which expands the skin's light sensitivity.

There are other new methods like lasers, that emphasize the useful results of light particularly on psoriatic sores. UV light therapy is the basic treatment with ultimate outcomes for treating psoriasis.

Systemic Therapy:

Systemic Therapy is majorly used in moderate to severe cases or when no response for, topical treatment and photo therapy is seen [6]. Those patients who undergo systemic treatment must have frequent blood and liver function tests since the medicines used are toxic [13]. Generally three main drugs are used in systemic treatment.

Methotrexate:

This is a popular anti-metabolite which is very effective agent used in treating severe psoriasis [13]. Irrespective of its benefits it has limitations as it is related with extreme acute and chronic adverse reactions that involve acute hematologic toxicity and acute and chronic hepatotoxicity. This treatment should be restricted to patients with disabling, refractory psoriasis. [17]

Cyclosporine:

It is a cyclic polypeptide and mostly used in organ transplantation as an immunosuppressant. It shows inhibitory effects on T-cells and acts on psoriasis. Cyclosporine should be limited for patients with severe psoriasis. Major side effects associated with this drug are nephrotoxicity and hypertension. Risk of malignancies may be increased. [13]

Acitretin:

Acitretin is an oral retinoid which act by its anti-inflammatory action. It shows good effect on combining with topical agents or light therapy in the generalized pustular and erythrodermic types of psoriasis [5] Though this drug has related teratogenic risk which exists for two to three years after terminating therapy it is the safest systemic treatment for psoriasis. [13]

Treatment using Biologics:

Biologics are means that inhibit molecular steps vital in the pathogenesis of this disease. They have grown in past few years as a good substitute therapeutic choices in treating psoriasis. They are of 2 types: agents that target the cytokine tumour necrosis factor α (example, adalimumab, etanercept) and agents that target T cells or antigen presenting cells (example, efalizumab). Though they have to be administered parentally, they are widely accepted by patients due to dissatisfaction with other treatments [18] and have led to high demand.

Combination Therapy

Combining various therapies like topical, photo, and systemic often results in reduction of doses of each therapy and can result in increased effectiveness. Therefore, physicians are focusing more on combination therapy. [27]

Herbal Therapy:

Plants and its constituents are used in herbal therapy which has less side effects than synthetic drugs. These days, herbal resources play an important role in the management of the skin and inflammatory diseases. [13]

Advantages:

- Increases therapeutic value by reducing toxicity and side effects
- Easily available
- More effectiveness

Disadvantages:

- High cost
- Difficulty in scaling up
- Have toxicity and stability issues

There are many herbal drugs which show anti psoriatic effect.

Wrightia tinctoria:

It is commonly known as Dyer's oleander, Indrajau and belongs to the family Apocynaceae. Leaves has astringent, anti inflammatory and anti bacterial properties and is used in treating various skin disorders [19]. From leaves of this plant a hydro alcoholic extract was obtained which shows antipsoriatic effect. This extract has a good antioxidant activity. These leaves contain beta amyryn and glucoside, which are reasonable for the skin healing properties of plant. [22]

Silybum marianum:

Its common name is Milk Thistle and belongs to the family Asteraceae. Liver neutralizes certain toxins associated with psoriasis. This herb increases liver function and prevents outbreak of psoriasis. It may prevent human T-cell activation that is normally seen in this disorder[13]. Active ingredient which protects liver is Silymarin, a chemical constituent extracted from the seeds. Silymarin consists of a group of flavonoids (Silibinin, Silidianin and Silicristin) that repairs hepatic cells [23].

Aloe vera:

It belongs to the family Asphodelaceae. The gel and the rind of the aloe vera leaf contains pharmacologically active components like anthraquinone and acemannan which have properties like analgesic, anti inflammatory, anti pruritic, wound healing etc. and hence can be used in treating psoriasis [13, 19].

Aloe vera moisturizes skin by forming a protective layer which prevents bacterial growth. Salicylic acid is a proven antiseptic agent used in psoriasis treatment which is present in Aloe vera [24, 25].

Work done on aloe vera states that 0.5% Aloe vera extract in a hydrophilic cream was well tolerated and found to be very effective [26].

Angelica sinensis: [19]

It is commonly known as Dong quay and belongs to the family Apiaceae. Extracts of this herb contains furocoumarin, i.e, Psoralen which acts as a potent photosensitizer in existence of ultraviolet A. Exposure to UVA along with Psoralen consumption leads to cross linking of epidermal DNA which reduces epidermal DNA synthesis rate.

Capsicum annum:

It is commonly known as Cayenne and belongs to the family Solanaceae. Major component is capsaicin. Substance- P (SP) mediates a neurogenic inflammatory condition which occurs in psoriasis [19].

Capsaicin decreases neurotransmitters from the sensory nerves and thus reduces pain and itching associated with psoriasis [27].

Smilax china:

It is commonly known as China root, which belongs to the family Smilacaceae. Rhizome part of the plant is used and this contains flavonoid quercetin which can be isolated from the methanolic extract. This flavonoid shows antipsoriatic activity by reducing epidermal thickness, which is due to reduction of leucocyte migration [19, 20, 28].

Ulmus rubra: [20]

It is commonly known as slippery elm and belongs to the family Ulmaceae. It contains a mucilage component which is derived from the inner bark of the elm.

Mahonia aquifolium:

It belongs the family Berberidaceae and is commonly called as Oregon grape. Bark extract of this drug is used which consists of berberine, berbamine, oxycanthine as major constituents. It inhibits keratinocytes growth [19, 21].

Alkaloids like berberin, protoberberine, berbamine and oxycanthine that are present in the root and bark extract of this plant have very good antimicrobial and antifungal activity. These alkaloids arrest the proliferation of various tumour cells as well as incorporate powerful antioxidant activity which hinders keratinocytes and reduces inflammation. [29]

Nigella sativa:

It is commonly known as black cumin and belongs to the family Ranunculaceae . 95% of ethanol extract of seeds of this herb shows significant epidermal differentiation and reduces epidermal thickness [19].

A study conducted on seed extract of this plant on an animal model of psoriasis, in which the histological effects were examined has shown that *Nigella sativa* has anti-psoriatic activity [30].

Thespesia populnea:

It is commonly known as ortia tree and belongs to the family Malvaceae. It has been traditionally used in treatment of psoriasis along with other skin disorders like ring worm, eczema, scabies etc. Oil which is obtained by boiling the bark in coconut oil is applied externally in scabies psoriasis [31].

In one study the screening for anti psoriatic activity was carried out by topically applying various extracts and isolated compounds like TpF-1, TpF-2 and TpS-2 [32].

Apart from the above mentioned drugs many other herbal drugs are used in treatment of psoriasis like *Matricaria recutita*, *Curcuma longa*, *Alpinia galangal*, *Indigo naturalis*, *Gaultheria procumbens*, *Cassia tora*, *Momordica charantia* etc. All these drugs show significant anti psoriatic effect by following different mechanism pathways.

Nutritional Therapy:

To reduce severity of psoriasis, more water should be consumed. Lots of green leafy vegetables should be taken which will reduce the intensity of this condition [13]. Few foods trigger the disease and they should be avoided. Eg: Coke, Vit-C, junk food, oily food, red meat, acidic food etc. Psoriasis worsens in those people who follow poor diet. Consumption of alcohol is proved to be a probability component for this disorder in men. Avoiding gluten (found in wheat, barley) is also good. Fumaric acid, fish oil, triglycerides, Vit-D, folic acid are found to be effective against psoriasis [33, 34].

Hydro therapy: [27]

Hydro or Water therapy is used as alternative therapy for psoriasis in which the skin is supplied with moisture, heat and certain minerals. The use of warm water for bathing improves blood circulation. Water rich in sulphur and other minerals should be used for bathing which will tend the skin.

To prove water therapy works in treating psoriasis, the sufferers were made to bathe in the Dead sea which is rich in salt and minerals and due to presence of ultraviolet light radiation the location was perfect for sunbathing.

Role of Nanotechnology in treating Psoriasis:

Nano particles are the colloidal systems with particle size varying from 10 nm to 1000nm. These are nano or sub nano sized structures which are made of synthetic or semi synthetic polymers. Nanoparticles of plant medicine is gaining a lot of attention currently [35].

Herbal drug delivery has certain problems due to poor solubility, low bioavailability, instability in biological medium and high first pass metabolism and poor permeability. Nanotechnology is useful to overcome all these problems [36, 37].

Merits of plant nanoparticle delivery system: [38, 39]

- Delivery of formulation to the targeted site
- Drug solubility and Pharmacokinetics can be improved by encapsulating the drugs within nanoparticles
- Bioavailability of drugs can be increased
- Degradation of drugs can be avoided
- Delivering the drug in small particle size increases the surface area of the drugs which allocates quicker dissolution in the blood
- Decreases side effects
- Decreases the dose of the formulation

Approaches of NanoTechnology:

Polymeris nanoparticles, Solid lipid nanoparticles, Liposomes, Proliposomes, Niosomes, Liquid crystalline systems, Quantum dots etc are the various approaches of nanotechnology.

Herbal constituents :**Various constituents that possess anti psoriatic activity are isolated from many herbal plants.**

- Artesunate is an active constituent which is derivative of Artemisinin that is processed from plant *Artemisia annua* L. of family Asteraceae. It acts by controlling the expression of CXCR2 and increases the secretion of TGF β , in vitro [40].
- Capsaicin is derived from *Capsicum annum* of family Solanaceae [41].
- Colchicine, an active constituent *Colchicum autumnale* of family Colchicaceae [42].
- Curcumin is derived from *Curcumin longa* belonging to the family Zingiberaceae shows its activity as selective phosphorylase kinase inhibitor, thereby decreasing inflammation through inhibition of NF κ B [43].
- Psoralen, is derived from *Psoralea corylifolia* of family Fabaceae. It inhibits epidermal DNA synthesis and thereby cell division [44].
- Koumine is derived from plant *Gelsemium elegans* belonging to the family Loganiaceae. It acts by inhibiting epidermal cell proliferation, promoting formation of granular cells, decreasing serum IL-2 levels [45].

Some other constituents derived from various plants are Iso-Camptothecin Hypericin, Podophyllotoxin, Isoquinoline etc [46, 47, 48, 49].

Herbal anti psoriatic formulations:

Several anti psoriatic herbal formulations are available and few of them are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Anti psoriatic Herbal formulations.

Formulation	Mode of action
Ginkgo and megranate (Chinese in vitro medicine)	Downregulates the expression of VEGF and PIGF [50]
Composite Shendi decoction (CSDD) and Diyin tablet (DYT) (Chinese formulation)	Serum IL-8 and plasma endothelin level reduced [51]
Chunghyuldan (Scutellariae Radix, Coptidis Rhizoma, Phellodendri Cortex, Gardeniae Fructus, Rhei Rhizoma) (Chinese formulation)	Regulation of COX-II produced by macrophage cells, and IFN- γ and IL-4 produced by T cells [52]
Lixue xiaoyin decoction (Chinese formulation)	Improves microcirculation and inhibits division of epidermal cells [53]
Qingdai compound capsule (Chinese formulation)	Decrease in expression of c-myc in keratinocytes [54]
Quyín granule (Chinese formulation)	Inhibition of faster epidermal cell proliferation and improvement of parakeratotic epidermal cells [55]
Radix Sophorae Flavescens (Sophora flavescens Ait.)	Inhibition of hyperplasia of epidermis cells and the promotion to the formation of granular layer [56]

Other herbal formulations which are used in treating psoriasis are Yinxie capsules, Tuhuai extract, Relieva, Vitamin B12 cream containing Avocado oil etc [57, 58, 59, 60].

Patents on antipsoriatic herbal products:

List of patents on anti psoriatic herbal products are given in table 2.

Table 2: Patents on anti psoriatic herbal formulations.

Composition	Formulation
Carthami tinctorii Flores, Guaiacum officinale, Pardanthe dichotoma Radices, Parmeliae herba of moss, Pyrus baecate	Chinese medicinal composition [61]
Herba Chelidonii (Chelidonium majus)	Topical emulsion or ointment [62]
Et Hg thiosalicylate, plantain extract, rose extract, orange extract	Topical composition [63]
Arnica Herb, marigold, Fructus Rhodomyrti, Radix Hamamelis Mollis, Avocado	Medicinal ointment [64]
Turmeric extract, α -hydroxy acids, α 1-antitrypsin	Topical formulation [65]
Moisturizing cream, berberine, oleuropein, glucosamine	Cream [66]
Mussel, Carnis Rapanae Thomasianae, Concha Ostreae, Concha Meretricis Seu Cyclinae, Liushugu, Scolopendra	Topical or oral composition [67]
Psorberine (M. aquifolium alcohol-water extract)	Topical formulation [68]
Mimosine and idebenone	Occlusive patch, cream, gel, emulsion, spray [69]
Wrightia tinctoria oil extract	Hydrophobic topical formulation (cream, ointment) [70]

Other than those listed in above table, many more patents are present which are claimed on antipsoriatic herbal formulations.

Future scope:

Use of herbal drugs in treatment of psoriasis is gaining importance gradually. So, dosage forms which can overcome the present existing disadvantages of herbal formulations can be prepared. Among them nanoparticles occupy the first place. Researchers and scientists are currently working to develop nanoparticulate drug delivery systems that can treat psoriasis with minimal side effects.

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